

TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The aim of the project is to develop a 100% autonomous system – a UAV (multicopter) – that can perform tasks without any human intervention. The core of the system is that the aerial device can be activated by alarm, schedule, or randomly to carry out its missions. These missions may include surveillance, monitoring, photogrammetry, or practically any task achievable with a UAV equipped with cameras, sensors, and detectors.

The essential feature of the system is full automation, which also provides its innovative edge. It is capable of flying along a predefined path using coordinates, returning to the base, and transmitting live video footage to the operator. The operation of the aircraft is fully automated, including precise landing at the base station and automatic charging there, ensuring 24/7 availability without human presence.

In the first phase of the project, we explored available similar technologies and found that there are relatively few working solutions that meet our goals. We mostly found experimental approaches, university projects, or amateur attempts. More advanced solutions existed only in theory or were presented via visual concepts or demo videos; we did not find any ready-to-purchase, product-level solutions.

We needed to identify which available technologies could help us achieve our objectives. One key decision was whether GPS technology alone would be sufficient to ensure accurate return to base. We investigated this and found that while GPS is necessary, it is not sufficient alone to guarantee centimeter-level landing accuracy. The drone's rough position must be corrected optically during descent to ensure precision landing. The base station must therefore be known with centimeter-level accuracy, requiring a GPS receiver capable of delivering real-time, high-precision coordinates. Selecting and acquiring such components was relatively straightforward, as existing commercial products could be integrated into our system.

Another prerequisite for centimeter-accurate landing is that the flight controller must support optical correction. We examined two major groups/types of systems to assess their suitability for integration.

DJI products are equipped with sensors and technologies that could, in theory, perform the necessary tasks. However, their system is highly closed. Even with the provided SDK, we could not find a way to integrate it seamlessly. We tested available products and evaluated the reliability of optical landing. DJI's system performed reliably, but it could not be modified or further developed without dismantling it. As such, we opted to use their Inspire 2 model for its sensors and cameras to build a custom system. We scheduled its acquisition around December, planning to start building the helicopter then.

The other major system we examined was the Ardupilot/Pixhawk group. These are open-source, community-developed flight controllers, fully integrable and customizable, with extensive documentation and support. However, they are not ready-made products, so everything must be built from scratch.

Whichever controller we ultimately choose, the top priority was ensuring the UAV could return to the base with the required accuracy.

Another important task was determining the specifications of the tools and technologies needed for prototype development, including the suitability of 3D printing and CNC technologies. After careful consideration, we concluded that 3D printing was suitable for our needs. The market offers a wide range of tools, so we evaluated the limits and key parameters of this technology and selected Makerbot as our manufacturer of choice. We initiated the procurement process accordingly.

Our first prototype helicopter was based on the Pixhawk controller. We defined the key parameters, flight time, battery capacity, and propeller sizing. We investigated the availability of components and finalized the specifications. During 3D design of the frame, we considered the physical requirements necessary for accurate landing. A beta prototype was built focusing purely on functionality—ignoring aesthetics or production readiness—to simulate the core capabilities of future versions.

We began testing basic functions, followed by autonomous operations, and finally subjected the system to stress tests and disruptive scenarios. We tested in harsh conditions like strong wind and cold temperatures, mapped out the radio signal limitations, and fine-tuned the system using flight logs and data. The process took considerable time, but ultimately we created a stable UAV capable of autonomous missions.

To achieve centimeter-accurate landing, we built an optical system comprising a ground-based infrared emitter and a receiver attached to the flight controller. This allowed the drone to approach the ground unit with centimeter precision. We resolved the power supply and mechanical protection of the emitter, then calibrated the receiver—a process that took longer than anticipated. We also had to program the communication between the receiver and the flight controller.

We then dedicated significant time to deliberately inducing system failures. Many such scenarios were successfully handled; others led to valuable insights and configuration adjustments. We did occasionally crash units, but we were prepared and worked tirelessly to maximize airborne testing hours. We tested for accuracy and introduced disruptive factors such as Wi-Fi interference and real-life environmental conditions like bad weather and low light. Eventually, we mapped the system's limitations.

We assembled an initial prototype that met most functional expectations but lacked aesthetic and design maturity. We sought external help from an R&D company, which created graphic and 3D designs based on our physical parameters and expectations. These refined designs retained the integrability of technological components while improving the form factor. We hope these plans will lead to the finalized product version.

Project Outcome

The result of this project may include multiple products. From the core concept, various customized UAV systems can be developed, optimized for specific missions—ranging from simple monitoring to industrial site surveillance with integrated security systems.

Target markets for distribution include the United Kingdom, Spain, Germany, and Hungary. We have strong networks in these countries, especially emphasizing our existing Spanish company (UAV Instruments Factory), which will serve as the main distribution channel.

Summary

At this stage of the project, we have resolved the major technical challenges. Despite some dead ends, we progressed at a steady, predictable pace, and collaboration among the team remained strong throughout. We've learned a great deal from each other, the technologies involved, and our mistakes. The prototype meets the project's original functional expectations. While there is still work ahead, we have solved the core issues. With the base system nearly complete, we are confident in our ability to carry the project forward. Although the funding period has ended, our commitment remains as strong as ever.

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